

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INCOME LEVEL AND PARENTAL EDUCATION WITH PRIMARY DENTAL CARIES EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

The main problem of oral health of primary school children is dental caries. Dental caries can be influenced by external factors, one of which is the level of income and education. The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between parents' income and education levels with the experience of primary dental caries at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City. Type of observational analytic research with cross sectional design. The study population was all 123 students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, sampling using saturated sample technique that met the inclusion criteria so that a sample of 114 people was obtained. Data collection by checking the def-t index, as well as filling out questionnaires by parents. Data analysis used univariate and bivariate analysis with chi square statistical test. The results showed that respondents with the highest parental income level with low criteria were 73.7%, for the highest level of parental education at low criteria were 47.7% and the most dental caries experience with poor criteria were 63.2%. The statistical test results obtained a p-value of income level of $0.00 < 0.05$ and education level of $0.03 < 0.05$. The conclusion of the study is that there is a relationship between parents' income and education levels with permanent dental caries. It is recommended for parents to do dental fillings with indications of fillings and increase knowledge and insight in terms of oral health.

Keywords: Primary dental caries, income level, education level.

1. INTRODUCTION

The most common oral disease suffered by humans is dental caries. However, many people still ignore the treatment for this caries, about 510 million cases of untreated primary dental caries (WHO, 2022). Dental caries is a condition of dental hard tissue disease. Dental caries begins with the formation of small holes or soft spots on the outside of the tooth, such as in the pit, fissure and interproximal area, if untreated dental caries can spread deeper into the pulp area (Tarigan, R. 2014).

According to the 2018 Riskesdas data, the prevalence of caries in Indonesia reached 88.8%. In the 5-9 years age group, the prevalence was 92.6%, with an average of 0.7, indicating that each child had one carious tooth. Meanwhile, in the 10-14 years age group, the caries prevalence reached 73.4%, with an average of 1.8, meaning that each child had caries in 1-2 teeth (Balitbankes, 2018a). In West Sumatra Province, the prevalence of caries is 43.87%. In the 5-9 years age group, the prevalence reached 50.19%, while in the 10-14 years age group it was 41.74%. In Bukittinggi City, the caries prevalence was recorded at 43.23%

(Balitbankes, 2018b). This can affect children's concentration at school and reduce their appetite, which in turn affects their nutritional status and leads to physical impairment. All of this has the potential to reduce the child's quality of life (Handayatun, N.N and Fitria, K.T. 2022).

Children aged 6-12 years usually have a combination of primary and permanent teeth in their mouths. The remaining primary teeth will naturally fall out to make room for the growing permanent teeth. Parents need to take good care of their child's baby teeth, even though they will eventually fall out. Primary teeth are prone to caries. This is due to the thinner, denser enamel structure and irregular shape, which makes deciduous teeth damage faster, more extensively and more severely than permanent teeth. The condition of primary teeth also affects the growth of the child's permanent teeth (Fithriyana, R. 2021). The high caries rate in children is also influenced by parental income and education, which play an important role in health status. High-income groups are more likely to be able to cover living expenses and have better access to health services than low-income and low-education groups (Suryani, L. 2020).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), socioeconomic conditions have a major influence on a person's opportunities, choices, and actions in caring for oral health. Worldwide, the average prevalence of cavities in primary teeth stands at 43%, with the highest number of cases being in lower-middle-income countries, at around 244 million cases, while high-income countries recorded the lowest number, at 45 million cases. Overall, untreated caries are more prevalent in lower-middle-income countries, where health systems and resources for treatment are often inadequate. (WHO, 2022). This study aims to explore the relationship between parents' income and education levels with dental caries experience at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City in 2024.

2. METHODOLOGY

The type of research is quantitative with an observational analytic design. The method used is cross sectional, which means that researchers see and measure variables at one specific time or at the same time (Carsel, S. 2018). A portion of the population is called a sample, which is taken based on certain characteristics or numbers. Sampling is done in a certain way, so that the sample can be considered as a representation or general description of the population (Kurniawan, A. 2018).

The sampling technique used in this study was saturated sampling technique, involving 114 respondents. However, there were 9 children who did not participate due to absence during the study. Data was collected using primary data, which is data obtained directly from respondents through direct examination and filling out questionnaires by parents. Income level was measured and categorized into very low, low, medium, high and very high. Meanwhile, education level was categorized into low, medium, and high. For dental caries examination, the results were categorized into good and bad. Data analysis used the chi square test with a significance level of $\alpha < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Frequency distribution of parents' income level at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City

Figure 1: Frequency Distribution of Student Parents' Income Level SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh Bukittinggi City Year 2024

Based on Figure 1, the frequency distribution of respondents' parents' income level shows that the majority are in the low category with a percentage of 73.7%, while the least are in the high category, which is 7%. The results of research on the income level of parents of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh students in Bukittinggi City show that the majority of parents are in the low income category. This low income can be influenced by the type of work they have, where the work they do may not provide opportunities to get high wages. Some jobs in the informal sector, although requiring a large amount of labor, still provide low wages due to limited working hours, so there is no time to look for additional work. In addition, the income received is often unstable and dependent on daily conditions.

Low income tends to affect the welfare of individuals or community groups, making it difficult for them to fulfill basic needs such as food, shelter, education and health services. When income is only sufficient for basic needs, spending on things beyond that, including education and access to health services, is limited. This low income is often due to the type of work that does not provide results proportional to the labor expended, so income remains low. Low productivity levels also mean that parents have little ability to save. This inability to save hinders investment and leads to low capital formation, which in turn worsens economic conditions and increases the risk of poverty (Soelistyo, A. 2023).

Low human resources are an additional factor that leads to low community income. This makes it difficult to find work and has an impact on the income earned. Skills and productivity are interconnected and affect income (Simanjuntak, D.A. 2018). The results of the study show that 7% of parents have a high income, which means they have the ability to access dental health care facilities for their children and buy foods that are good for oral health. Parents with high income can take various steps to prevent dental caries in children, such as fluoride application and fissure sealant treatment to prevent caries. Healthy eating habits also play a role in caries prevention, for example calcium-rich foods such as milk can strengthen tooth enamel, while fiber-rich fruits and vegetables play a role in cleaning teeth and gums, helping to prevent food debris from sticking to the surface of the teeth that can trigger caries. (Frethernety, A., Jelita, H., and Nugrahini, S. 2023). The results of this study are in line with previous research in 2019 on the

Relationship between Education Level and Family Head Income with Child Dental Caries in the Seubun Ayon Village Community, Lhoknga District, Aceh Besar, which showed that most of the parents' income was in the low category, namely 56.5%. (Suryani, L. 2020).

3.2 Frequency distribution of parents' education level at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City

Figure 2. Frequency Distribution of Student Parents' Education Level SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh Bukittinggi City Year 2024

Figure 2 explains that the frequency distribution of respondents' parents' education level was mostly in the low criteria at 47.4%, and the least in the high criteria at 14%. Based on the results of research on the education level of parents of students at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City, it was found that 47.4% of parents were in the low education category. This shows that most parents have a low level of education. This low level of education can be caused by various factors, such as limited economic resources, a less supportive social environment, different life priorities, and low interest in continuing education. Low interest in education often leads to a lack of motivation to learn and achieve good academic performance. People with low interest in education tend to ignore learning opportunities and do not realize the importance of education in improving quality of life. These factors are interrelated and contribute to limitations in obtaining higher education.

Low levels of education are not caused by one factor alone. Lack of access to education, such as limited facilities and the number of educators, cannot always be overcome by simply increasing facilities and teachers. This problem is also related to population growth and its distribution. Low education is reflected in the low quality of human resources (HR), which in turn leads to low income and poverty. These conditions then limit one's ability to access education and health services (Syah, N. and Hendri, Y. 2021). Economic factors are one of the main causes of people dropping out of school, due to the high cost of continuing education to a higher level.

Another factor that causes the low level of formal education that a person pursues is the social environment and interests. The environment and society play an important role in shaping how a person grows and develops. The background at home, such as parental attitudes, family harmony and support for children's interest in higher education, contribute to shaping an individual's personality and mindset. Therefore, attention to one's social environment is very important so that education runs well and smoothly (Kahar, A. 2020).

The results of this study are in line with a previous study in 2018 regarding "The Relationship between Education Level, Income, Knowledge, and Parental Attitudes Towards Permanent First Molar Dental Caries Status" in third grade students of SD

Negeri 25 Lubuk Lintah, Kuranji District, Padang City. The study found that 89.5% of parents had a low level of education (Harsyaf, C.C and Yandi, S. 2018).

3.3 Frequency distribution of primary tooth caries experience at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Students' Primary Dental Caries Experience SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh Bukittinggi City in 2024

Criteria	f	%	Component def-t			def-t	Average
			d	e	f		
Good	42	36,8%	3	2	1	6	0,05
Ugly	72	63,2%	252	76	0	328	2,85
Total	114	100%	255	78	1	334	2,9
Average			2,2	0,7	0,009	2,9	

Table 6 shows that the frequency distribution of primary tooth caries experience was highest among respondents in the bad category, at 63.2%, while the least was in the good category, at 36.8%. The highest component is decay (d) with an average of 2.2, which indicates that each child has 2-3 teeth that have caries with indications that need to be filled.

Based on the results of research on the experience of primary dental caries in students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City, it was found that 63.02% of children were in the bad category, which means that most children have caries-free teeth less than 90%. The high percentage of caries-free teeth < 90% in elementary school children, especially those in grade one, is generally due to the fact that they are not yet able to independently maintain their personal health. Children who have not been able to maintain personal hygiene tend to have poor oral and dental conditions, one of which has dental caries. Another factor is the inappropriate time to brush: many children brush their teeth every morning before going to bed, but brushing should be done at least twice a day, after breakfast and before going to bed at night.

Keeping baby teeth healthy is important for a child's dental health throughout their life. Since most children are not yet capable of self-care, parents should teach children oral hygiene. Children should be taught dental health in a fun way so that they do not feel forced and are more receptive to the lessons (Ardani, I.G. 2018). Parents need to help their children brush their teeth twice a day: once in the morning after breakfast and once in the evening before bed, this helps keep the child's teeth and mouth healthy. It is very important for children to brush their teeth well to keep their teeth clean. Regular brushing helps prevent plaque from sticking to the teeth, plaque on the teeth can cause cavities (Sukmawati, A.S et al., 2023).

The food that children eat is also an influential factor, and this is strongly influenced by the family and school environment. Children at primary school age begin to follow their own desires, such as trying different types of food. Observations of food sold in school canteens and outside of school show that many vendors sell sweet and sticky foods such as candy, chocolate, biscuits and ice. In addition, almost all students buy

these foods during school breaks. They also do not have the habit of rinsing their mouth after eating sweet and sticky foods, which increases the risk of dental caries.

Children at primary school age have a tendency to love sweet foods such as candy, cotton candy and chocolate; however, if children do not clean their teeth regularly, especially if they do not rinse their mouths after eating sweet and sticky foods, this problem will get worse. Eating a lot of sugar can cause dental caries. The formation of extracellular polysaccharides is triggered by excessive amounts of digested sugar, which produces acids that convert sugar into acid. These polysaccharides adhere to the tooth surface, making plaque difficult to remove. Good brushing habits are also very important to prevent caries because how you brush your teeth affects the likelihood of caries appearing. Caries can appear as a result of food debris left in the mouth without being cleaned (Marlindayanti *et al.*, 2022).

Children with mixed dentition often experience dental and oral problems. At this age, it is important to pay more attention to oral health as this can affect their concentration in learning and their academic performance at school. To assess the condition of primary teeth and caries experience, 6-7 years old is used as a reference. At this age, permanent teeth begin to erupt and require special attention to avoid premature decay that may affect the child's quality of life in the future (Gestina, Y and Meilita, Z. 2020). A family or school environment that allows children to eat foods that cause caries and ignores the importance of nutritional intake is a major risk factor for dental caries. It is very important for parents to supervise what their children eat every day and help them take care of their teeth. Thus, they can avoid cavities. This study found that 36.8% of children had more than 90% caries-free teeth, which shows that most children are doing well. They have tried to avoid caries, such as reducing sweet and sticky foods, brushing their teeth twice a day after breakfast and before bed, and getting used to rinsing their mouths after eating sweet foods. To reduce the risk of caries, you can reduce the consumption of sweet and sticky foods, use toothpaste that contains fluoride, and apply flour to the teeth (Putri, Herijulianti and Neneng, 2015).

Previous research in 2019 in TanjungSari District Sumedang examined the characteristics of caries in children aged 6-7 years with mixed teeth. The study revealed that the average caries experience in primary teeth was 8.67, indicating that each child had 8-9 teeth with caries. Most of the respondents had teeth with a caries-free condition of less than 90%, which fell into the poor category. The data from the study also showed that the most common caries component was decay (Prisind, D. *et al.*, 2019).

3.4 The relationship between parents' income level and the experience of primary dental caries at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City

Table 2: Relationship between Parents' Income Level and Dental Caries Experience
Eldest Student of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City in 2024

Parent's income level	Kriteria def-t				Total	%	p-Value
	Good		Ugly				
	f	%	f	%			
Low	26	22,8%	58	50,9%	84	73,7%	0.00
Medium	8	7%	14	12,3%	22	19,3%	
High	8	7%	0	0%	8	7%	
Very High	0	0	0	0%	0	0%	

Total	42	36,8%	72	63,2%	114	100%
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Based on table 2, it is known that most parents' income is in the low category at 73.3%, with the highest level of def-t in the bad category at 50.9% and the lowest in the good category at 22.8%. The chi square statistical test shows a p-value of 0.00 <0.05, which means that there is a significant relationship between parental income and the experience of primary dental caries in students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh.

Based on the results of research on the relationship between parents' income level and the experience of primary dental caries in students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City, it was found that most respondents were in the low income category, which was 73.3%. The highest def-t category was found in poor condition, at 50.9%, while the good category was only 22.8%. This shows that the level of dental caries in children is higher if the parents' income is lower. This finding was also statistically proven with a p-value of 0.00, indicating a significant relationship between parental income level and primary dental caries.

Low parental income can affect the condition of primary dental caries in children due to limited access to dental health care. People with low income may find it difficult to visit dental health facilities regularly or get the necessary preventive care. Awareness about the importance of dental care is often neglected because they may feel that they do not need to take action if they do not experience pain. In addition, the habit of eating high-sugar foods, which is often associated with low income, can also increase the risk of dental caries. People with low income usually experience more caries cases due to difficulties in accessing oral care facilities, lack of awareness about the importance of dental visits, or limitations in obtaining the desired facilities. Socioeconomic factors affect the opportunities and choices available as well as behaviors in maintaining oral health. Individuals with low income often neglect their oral health care.

Dietary intake also affects caries risk in low-income individuals, as they may not be able to afford foods that are good for oral health. Although the cost of dental treatment can be covered by BPJS, not all procedures are covered. Low-income people who cannot afford the cost of drugs and medical devices outside the coverage of health insurance face obstacles. As health insurance does not cover all services, low levels of health are ultimately reflected in indicators such as mortality and life expectancy (Sahar, J., Setiawan, A. and Riasmini, N.M., 2019). Income has a direct impact on access to medical care, where increased income also allows for increased health care costs. Children from low-income families are more susceptible to dental caries than children from low-income families. This is related to the lack of awareness of a healthy lifestyle among people with low income (Suryani, L. 2020).

Previous research in 2022 at Dharma Wanita Persatuan Tambakrejo 1 Kindergarten showed a relationship between parents' income level and the incidence of caries in children, with a p-value of 0.029. This finding shows that children of parents with low income tend to have higher caries rates (Vony Kusuma Fadia, I., Prasetyowati, S. and Hadi, S. 2022). Another study conducted in 2021 examined the relationship between parents' socioeconomic status and the incidence of primary dental caries in children aged 4-5 years in Kuok Village. The study found that there was a relationship between parents' income level and the incidence of primary dental caries, with a p-value

of 0.033. From the study, it was found that among parents with low economic status, 18 (94.7%) children had dental caries (Fithriyana, R 2021).

3.5 The relationship between parents' education level and the experience of primary dental caries at SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City

Table 3: Relationship between Parents' Education Level and the Experience of Primary Dental Caries Students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City in 2024

Parent's Educations Level	Kriteria def-t				Total	%	p- Value
	Good		Ugly				
	f	%	f	%			
Low	15	13,2%	39	34,2%	54	47,4%	0.039
Medium	17	14,9%	27	23,7%	44	38,6%	
High	10	8,8%	6	5,2%	16	14%	
Total	42	36,9%	72	63,1%	114	100%	

Based on table 3, it can be seen that the highest level of parental education is in the low category at 47.4%, with the highest level of def-t in the bad category at 34.2% and the lowest in the good category at 13.2%. The chi square statistical test shows a p-value of 0.039 < 0.05, which means that there is a significant relationship between the level of parental education and the experience of primary dental caries in students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City.

Based on research on the relationship between parents' education level and the experience of primary dental caries in students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City, a significant relationship was found between the two variables with a p-value of 0.039. Most respondents came from children with low-educated parents, which was 47.4%. In terms of def-t criteria, the poor category recorded the highest rate of 34.2%, while the good category was at the lowest rate of 13.2%.

The higher the education level of parents, the better the dental health of their children. Highly educated parents usually have a better understanding of caries prevention and tend to teach dental health practices to their children, so the risk of caries can be reduced. They are more receptive to information because of their critical thinking skills and openness to new knowledge. Education includes all efforts made by or for a person with the aim of shaping character, mind and physique towards perfection. Education also plays a role in maturing the intellectual, emotional, and human aspects continuously (Purwanti, D.E. and Almuji, 2017).

Education helps shape the way we act and think. When people go to school for a long time, they learn many things, which helps them understand the world better. For example, a well-educated mother can think more clearly and look for answers about why children get cavities. Thus, if caries occurs in children, the problem can be handled immediately (Afrianti, B., Anang and Nugroho, C. 2023). Preventive measures to reduce the risk of caries include: reducing the consumption of sweet and sticky foods, brushing teeth at least twice a day after breakfast and before bed, using fluoride toothpaste, applying fluoride, closing fissures in teeth that have been affected by caries, and routine dental check-ups to health facilities at least every six months (Putri, Herijulianti and Neneng, 2015).

The results of this study are in line with a 2020 study in Seibun Ayon Village, Lhoknga District, Aceh Besar, which found a significant relationship between parental education level and the incidence of dental caries in children, with a p-value of 0.047 (Suryani, 2020). The results of another study in the year at SDS Kemala Bhayangkari 2 Rantau Prapat showed a relationship between parental education level and the experience of primary dental caries, with a p-value of 0.015. This study also found that children with low educated parents tended to have higher caries status (Siagian, V.F., Tarigan, S. and Muharraran, F. 2022).

4. CONCLUSION

Berdasarkan hasil penelitian yang telah dilakukan pada Murid SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh Kota Based on the results of research that has been conducted on State Elementary School Students 08 Campago Ipuh Bukittinggi City, it can be concluded that:

- A. The income level of the respondents' parents was mostly in the low criteria, which amounted to 73.7%.
- B. The level of education of the respondents' parents was mostly in the low criteria at 47.4%.
- C. The caries experience of primary teeth is mostly in the bad criteria, namely 63.2% with an average def-t index of 2.9, meaning that children have 2-3 primary teeth with caries experience.
- D. There is a significant relationship between parents' income level and the experience of primary dental caries in students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City with a p-value of 0.00.
- E. There is a significant relationship between parents' education level and dental caries experience in students of SD Negeri 08 Campago Ipuh, Bukittinggi City with a p-value of 0.039.

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